

LINGUISTICS IN FUTURE ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHERS DEVELOPMENT OF COMPETENCIES IMPROVING METHODOLOGY

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11372349>

Abstract. *This article discusses methods and measures to improve the methods necessary for the development of language competencies among future English language teachers, mentioning various methods and techniques.*

Keywords: *linguistics, methodology, competence, development, lesson, method, goal, idea, research.*

In today's world, it has become very important to have a lot of knowledge. For this, it is very useful for a person to study the languages of the world. That's the point. The more languages a person knows, the more countries he will be in, the more he will know the world. In short, today there will be no shortage of people who know the language in order to be competitive. In foreign countries, it is especially useful for young people to learn English. The reason is that English is one of the world languages. At a time when Uzbekistan is developing, children are taught English from school. In particular, the head of state Sh.M. Mirziyoyev also says: "We are committed to building a competitive state, since we have set a goal, from now on graduates of schools, lyceums, colleges and universities should know about this." at least 2 foreign languages fluently According to them, in the decree of our president "On measures to bring activities to popularize the study of foreign languages in the Republic of Uzbekistan to a qualitatively new level" "In accordance with the state program, in order to develop the teaching of foreign languages as a priority area of educational policy, to radically improve the quality of education in this direction, to attract qualified teachers to the field, to increase the population's interest in learning foreign languages, a number of reforms are being implemented"[1].

Therefore, one of the most important tasks of every young generation is to adequately resist these efforts and not remain indifferent to them. In order to teach English to students, it is important to prepare young personnel who will teach them. There are many facilities opening up across our country for boys and girls who want to learn a language. In particular, state and non-state higher education institutions provide their services for training future English language teachers. a very responsible task. To do this, first of all, it is necessary to determine a number of teacher competencies, in particular, these include personal competence, professional competence and linguistic competence.

"Professional competence is the acquisition by a specialist of the knowledge, skills and abilities necessary to carry out professional activities, and the ability to apply them at a high level in practice. Professional competence is not the acquisition by a specialist of specific knowledge and skills. , but each is independent or related to the acquisition of integrative knowledge and learning activities. Also, competence requires constant enrichment of professional knowledge, assimilation of new information, understanding of important social requirements, search for new information, its processing and the ability to apply it in one's work" [2].

A specialist with real professional competence:

It constantly expands his knowledge;
It keeps abreast of new information;
It deeply understands the requirements of the time;
It independently seeks new knowledge;
It processes the knowledge sought and uses it accordingly in his professional activities.

The meaning of the terms competence and competency is still debated by a number of scientists. The term “competence” was one of the first to appear in English-language literature, and this term is used using the terms “knowledge”, “skill”, “ability”. The term “competence” is taken from the Latin language and is translated as “ability” in our native language. In the modern study of the term, the linguistic competence approach has been used since the middle of the 20th century and represents a set of knowledge, skills and abilities focused on activities in the process of using language. In the methodology of teaching foreign languages, concepts such as “knowledge”, “skills” and “competence” require an activity factor in the process of language use and learning efficiency. The totality of theoretical knowledge, skills and competencies acquired during the study of foreign languages represents the ability to independently apply them in practice, that is, in communicative communication.

Studying the theoretical foundations of English language teaching makes us think about the existing research on language competence today. Many scientists have still worked on the problem of linguistic competence. spelling, orthographic, punctuation norms of the language and types of speech activities (listening, speaking, reading and writing) for the ability to use the native language) refers to the ability to use it.

“The main problem is that phonetic and grammatical skills are formed by the teacher, and the student must work independently to expand their vocabulary. Undoubtedly, the process of mastering new words occurs in classes under the supervision of the teacher, but due to the limited time of classes, the teacher is not able to pay the necessary attention to this issue. using exercises through shaping. Mastering the skill of forming word combinations means mastering the ability to independently understand the meanings of unfamiliar words based on knowledge of the meanings of their components and the corresponding model of word formation” [3].

Every person who begins to study a foreign language must first of all remember the vocabulary of this language, that is, the words necessary to communicate in this foreign language. In the learning process, the main attention should be focused on maximizing the enrichment of students’ speech with new words. as far as possible, preparing them for the process of communication, teaching speech skills, achieving consistency and accuracy in speech, if students are able to understand the meaning of phrases and sentences, if they can express their thoughts orally and in writing, they can use synonyms without hesitation and use one word interchangeably in their speech.

“The most complete and accurate definition of language competence was given by the French researcher S. Moiran, referring to three aspects of language: phonetics, vocabulary, grammar. Moreover, he described the concept as including the ability to apply knowledge and skills in the practice of communication and to make correct grammatical utterances.”[1]

It is known to everyone that nowadays linguistic competence is considered as a set of specific knowledge and skills necessary for a person to perform speech acts. Linguistic competence includes the construction and understanding of sentences, as well as proficiency in language and linguistic competence is understood as a set of specific linguistic knowledge that provides the ability to use it for communication. development of the student's personality.

“The main means of developing competence in learning foreign languages are various technologies, methods and forms. The following methods of educational activity are less effective in learning foreign languages: monologue speech by the teacher, assignment by the teacher of homework from the textbook, showing a film, traditional test work. Instead of these methods, the demonstration method, discussions with students, game technology (role-playing, dramatic), the method of specific situations (case studies), problem discussion, group or team games, language portfolio, the use of audio-visual tools, Internet resources, multimedia are used. tools are more efficient. Discussion, discussion, role-playing games conducted by the teacher orally and in writing are methods of increasing the thinking abilities of students” [4].

In conclusion, we can say that an English teacher should explain to his students that a lesson is a good opportunity to use a foreign language in practice, and communication between students in English during a lesson is a factor that develops their language. competence should encourage them to do, correct their mistakes on time, and this kind of encouragement helps them develop self-confidence and overcome their fear.

Students are not allowed to exchange ideas with each other. But this method, in turn, is ineffective, as has been emphasized in the studies of many scientists. The teacher, creating a democratic atmosphere, expresses his opinion to the students without sharply denying them.

Regardless of the genre of literature, that is, drama, short story, novel, it is very useful for the development of communicative competence when teaching foreign languages. If they watch staged versions of these works performed by local English actors, helps students understand their pronunciation, cultural aspects, facial expressions of interaction. Such literary texts help to develop linguistic competence through vocabulary and grammatical rules, as well as to understand how a literary text appears in the context of English culture. Through storytelling, students develop both linguistic and communicative competence. In this, the teacher teaches the students a story and asks them to tell it to the class. Another way to engage students in situations that reflect real life abroad is to use English news, films, online TV lessons to show them how to use English history. Wide use of the local language in and outside the classroom, viewing and reading newspapers in English. These activities develop students' linguistic competence and introduce them to a variety of texts and vocabularies used outside of class.

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